

Title: Effects of a daily intake of calcium and vitamin D-enriched milk in healthy postmenopausal women: A randomized, controlled and double-blind nutritional study: The EFICALCIO Study.

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Abbreviations: BMD: bone mineral density; FOS: Fructooligosaccharides; OC: osteocalcin; P1NP: Procollagen I intact N-terminal; CTX: C-terminal telopeptide; BIA: bioelectrical impedance analysis; HOMA: homeostasis model assessment. LS; lumbar spine; FN: femoral neck; CRP: C reactive protein.

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ABSTRACT:

Aims: To determine the effect of the daily intake of calcium and vitamin D-enriched milk (with or without fructooligosaccharides (FOS) on vitamin D, bone metabolism and cardiovascular risk factors.

Methods: 2-year randomized controlled study, including 500 healthy postmenopausal women assigned to 500 ml/day of skimmed milk to one of three groups: Low-dose (L): (120 mg/100 ml calcium, vitamin D₃ 30 UI/100 mL), group A: calcium and vitamin D (180 mg/100 mL and 120 UI/100 mL) and group B: calcium and vitamin D (180 mg/100 mL and 120 UI/100 mL) and FOS (5 g/L). We evaluated serum 25(OH)D, bone mineral density by DXA, and biochemical data of glucose and lipid metabolism.

Results: After 24 months, vitamin D concentrations did not change in the control group but increased in group A and group B, $p < 0.001$. We observed an increase in femoral neck BMD ($p = 0.045$), and an improvement in fasting plasma glucose ($p = 0.010$), HbA_{1c} ($p < 0.001$), total cholesterol ($p < 0.001$), LDL cholesterol ($p < 0.001$) and Apo B100 ($p = 0.015$).

Conclusions: Daily intake of milk enriched with calcium and vitamin D in postmenopausal healthy women induces a significant improvement in vitamin D status, a significant increase in BMD at femoral neck and also favourable effects on glucose and lipid profile.

Keywords: calcium, vitamin D, postmenopausal, nutritional intervention.

Introduction

Postmenopausal women are at increased risk of bone loss¹ and cardiovascular events². Clinical studies in elderly women have shown that combined calcium and vitamin D supplementation can reduce the risk of fracture³. Menopause is associated with a deterioration in lipid profile, mainly a rise total cholesterol, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and apolipoprotein B, with substantial increases within the 1-year interval before and after the final menstrual period⁴. Low 25 OH vitamin D [25(OH)D] has been associated with an unfavourable lipid profile⁵, which could explain in part its relationship with cardiovascular disease and mortality. There is also a positive association between serum and insulin sensitivity evaluated by the glucose clamp technique^{6,7}, and a negative association between serum 25(OH)D and fasting plasma glucose⁸, glucose tolerance⁹ and HbA_{1c}¹⁰ has been shown in epidemiological studies.

In postmenopausal women current recommendations state an intake of 1200 mg of calcium every day in women between 51 and 70 years. Increasing calcium intake from dietary sources slightly increased bone mineral density (BMD) (by 0.6-1.8%) over one to two years at all sites, except the forearm where there was no effect. Increasing calcium intake from dietary sources increases BMD by a similar amount to increases in BMD from calcium supplements. In each case, the increases are small (1-2%) and non-progressive, with little further effect on BMD after a year.

The recommendations from the Endocrine Society suggest that all adults aged 50–70 years require at least 600 IU of vitamin D to maximize bone health and muscle function¹². However, only one in two postmenopausal women with osteoporosis who take calcium and/or vitamin D supplements have good self-reported therapeutic adherence to this treatment¹³. The adherence in healthy postmenopausal women may even be lower. Thus, nutritional strategies may improve adherence and consequently vitamin D intake and thus vitamin D concentrations.

Previous studies have addressed the effects of different nutritional interventions including vitamin D supplementation in postmenopausal women. Manios et al.¹⁴ showed that a 12 month-intervention with dairy products containing 300 IU/day of vitamin D₃ induced favourable changes in biochemical indexes of bone metabolism and bone mineral density compared to calcium alone. In another 6 week-long study from Bonjour et al.¹⁵, conducted in institutionalized women, the consumption of cheese containing 100 IU of vitamin D₃ induced a decrease in some markers of bone

resorption. In Chinese women ¹⁶, the intake of a drink with 900 mg of calcium and 256 IU of vitamin D₃ per day improved vitamin D status and reduced bone turnover over 12 weeks. However, results regarding changes in bone turnover markers and bone mineral density are not entirely consistent. Besides, most of these studies have had a short follow up.

The main objective of this study was to compare the effects of the regular consumption of a dairy product enriched with 900 mg/day of calcium and 600 IU/day of vitamin D₃, compared to those taking 600 mg of calcium and 150 IU of vitamin D₃, in serum concentrations of 25(OH)D and bone mineral density (BMD) in healthy postmenopausal women. Other objectives were to evaluate changes in anthropometric parameters, cardiovascular risk factors and glucose metabolism. Finally, a secondary objective was to analyse the effects of the addition of fructooligosaccharides (FOS) to vitamin D and calcium.

Subjects and methods

Healthy postmenopausal female volunteers from the general population were identified in three clinics of Spain. 508 women (aged 59.3 ± 5.6 years) were invited to participate in the study, and 500 accepted to participate. The inclusion criteria were menopause, age older than 55 years and no history of osteoporotic fractures. Exclusion criteria were the presence of renal, gastrointestinal, hepatic or endocrinological diseases, the presence of any serious illness, previous treatment with drugs affecting bone metabolism or lipid profile, current treatment with calcium and/or vitamin D supplements, allergy or intolerance to cows protein and expected poor compliance. Of them, 39 women were excluded from the study for having previously unknown medical conditions (9 type 2 diabetes, 10 primary hyperparathyroidism, 20 osteoporosis), which can affect bone metabolism. During follow up 94 women did not continue in the study (76 during the first year and 18 during the second year of the intervention), all of them for personal reasons. After that, 80% (n= 367) of women completed the study (Figure 1).

The Ethical Committee of Hospital Universitario San Cecilio of Granada approved the study. Informed written consent was obtained from the volunteers. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical rules of the Helsinki Declaration, following the EEC Good Clinical Practice guidelines (July 1996).

Study design:

This is a 24 months double-blinded and randomized nutritional intervention, to evaluate the effect of milk enriched in calcium and vitamin D on vitamin D plasma concentrations, bone parameters (bone mineral density (BMD) and bone turnover markers) and cardiovascular risk factors (glucose metabolism and lipid profile). Moreover, we aimed to compare the effects between the low-dose vitamin D (L) intervention arm and the higher dose intervention groups (A and B). In a previous study¹⁷ the positive effects of fructo-oligosaccharides (FOS) on calcium absorption has been tested. Thus, we also planned to evaluate differences in 25(OH)D changes according to the presence of FOS. The subjects were randomly assigned to one of three groups:

1) Low-dose group (L) (n = 152): semi-skimmed milk (calcium 120 mg/100 mL and vitamin D 30 IU/100 mL).

2) Vitamin D group (A) (n = 157): semi-skimmed milk enriched with calcium (180 mg/100 mL) and vitamin D (120 IU/100 mL).

3) Vitamin D+FOS group (B) (n = 152): semi-skimmed milk enriched with calcium (180 mg/100 mL), vitamin D (120 IU/100 mL) and FOS (5 g/L).

The three groups consumed the dairy drinks for 24 months (500mL/day in two intakes of 250mL), in the context of their usual diet. Counselling about Mediterranean diet and physical activity were provided to all women. Adherence to the intervention was confirmed every three months by telephone calls and by collection of empty containers. The dairy drinks were produced in white 1-L Tetra Bricks by Lactalis Puleva (Granada, Spain) so that neither the volunteers nor the researchers did know which dairy product was consumed.

Food frequency questionnaire:

The average dietary intake was evaluated by a food frequency questionnaire (7 days-nutritional survey and Frequency Questionnaire Food Consumption) at baseline, 12 months and 24 months.

Anthropometric measurements:

Anthropometric measurements were measured at the beginning of the study and after 6, 12 y 24 months of intervention. Body weight (kg) was measured using a standard balance beam (Seca). Body height (cm) was measured using a precision stadiometer (Seca), attached to the balance beam.

Biochemical parameters

Blood samples were taken at 0, 12 and 24 months after an overnight fast (i.e. a 12-h fast). For biochemical analyses, the blood was collected in SST-Vacutainer (BD) and serum was separated by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 15 min at 22-24 °C, divided into aliquots and frozen and stored at -80 °C until withdrawn for analysis.

Serum total cholesterol (TC), HDL-cholesterol (HDL-c), triglycerides (TG), glucose concentrations, HbA1c and apoB were determined by standard automated procedures (Biosystems Barcelona, Spain). LDL-cholesterol (LDL-c) was calculated using the Friedewald formula.

Bone-related parameters were measured by ELISA **at baseline, 12 months and 24 months**: intact-PTH (IBL International GMBH, Hamburgo, Alemania), carboxy-terminal collagen crosslinks (Immunodiagnostic System Ltd., Boldon, UK), osteocalcin (OC) (IBL International GMBH, Hamburgo, Alemania), procollagen amino-terminal propeptide type 1 (P1NP) (Immunodiagnostic System Ltd., Wuhan, China). Serum 25(OH)D concentrations were estimated by chemiluminescence immunoassay from Diasorin (LIAISON® 25 OH Vitamin D TOTAL Assay).

Skeletal muscle mass measurement

Skeletal muscle mass was estimated from bioelectrical impedance analysis (Tanita BC418) at baseline, and 12 months and 24 months after the intervention. This device calculates body fat percentage, fat mass, fat-free mass, and predicted muscle mass, on the basis of data obtained by Dual Energy X-ray Absorptiometry (DXA), using Bioelectrical Impedance Analysis (BIA), with an operating frequency of 50 kHz at 500 µA.

Bone mineral density measurement

DXA was carried out in all women at baseline and after 24 months of intervention. BMD in g/cm² was determined by DXA (NORLAND XR-800; variation coefficient 1-1.2%) at lumbar spine (L2-L4) and femoral neck. Women with osteoporosis according to WHO criteria were excluded from the study.

Statistical analyses:

Determination of the sample size was estimated from the effects on changes in serum 25(OH)D, which was the primary outcome of the trial. It was expected that a difference of 10% in serum 25(OH)D changes would be detected between the 2 groups with a power of 80% and 2-sided α of 0.05. Such a 10% difference in change in 25(OH)D required a sample of 150 participants per group, taking into account a standard deviation of inter-individual difference of 10% and an expected rate of drop-out of 15%. Data were assessed for normality and homogeneity of variance, and are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Comparisons of quantitative variables among groups were performed using Student's t test for independent samples (intergroup differences). Intergroup comparisons at the beginning of the study were assessed with an independent t test or with the Mann-Whitney test for the non-Gaussian variables. The effect of the milk product in each group at the different measurement time points was analysed by one-way repeated measures analysis of variance followed by Tukey post hoc test (within-group comparisons). Significant differences produced by the consumption of one or other milk product or by longitudinal effects were analysed by using 2-way repeated-measures analysis of variance followed by post hoc Tukey test. For the non-Gaussian variables, the Wilcoxon and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to assess intragroup and intergroup differences. When intergroup comparisons showed significant differences, an independent t test or Mann-Whitney test was applied to determine the time points at which the groups differed. Analysis was performed using SPSS software (version 17.0), and P values of less than 0.05 considered significant.

Results

Baseline clinical characteristics are shown in Table 1. There were not statistically significant differences in any of the parameters evaluated, with the exception of HDL-cholesterol that was significantly higher in group B compared to

group L.

Changes in average dietary intake

Compliance was above 85%. There were no significant changes in average dietary intake during the nutritional intervention. We did not observe any changes in other habits, evaluated by a questionnaire (data not shown).

Changes in vitamin D concentrations and PTH

We did not observe differences in baseline 25(OH)D concentrations according to the group. At 24 months, there was no increase in 25(OH)D concentrations in the low dose group: Baseline 22.0 ± 7.3 ng/ml vs 24 months 22.6 ± 7.0 ng/ml, $p = 0.245$. In women in the higher dose vitamin D₃ groups there was a significant increase in 25(OH)D concentrations during the nutritional intervention: Group A: baseline: 21.3 ± 6.8 ng/ml, 12 months: 27.0 ± 9.1 , 24 months: 26.6 ± 6.4 , Group B: baseline: 21.9 ± 9.5 ng/ml, 12 months: 27.2 ± 11.0 ng/ml, 24 months: 25.2 ± 6.2 ng/ml; $p < 0.001$ for the comparisons between baseline, 12 and 24 months in groups A and B. There were no differences in 25(OH)D concentrations between groups A and B, neither at 12 months ($p = 0.668$) nor at 24 months ($p = 0.881$) (Table 4), and no differences were observed in calcium concentrations (12 months $p=0.740$, 24 months $p=0.540$). We also analysed potential differences in changes in BMD according to the presence of FOS, with no differences in changes in BMD at 12 months (LS $p=0.576$, FN $p=0.064$) nor at 24 months (LS $p=0.594$, FN $p=0.209$). Thus, for further analysis we considered jointly patients in both groups of high-dose vitamin D intervention (groups A and B together).

At baseline, there were no differences in the percentage of patients with 25(OH)D concentrations above 20 ng/dl or 30 ng/dl. After the intervention, the percentage of women with adequate 25(OH)D concentrations was significantly higher in groups A (84.1 % at 12 months and 85.2 % at 24 months) and B (84.1 % at 12 months and 81.7% at 24 months) compared to L (Figure 2). Again, we did not observe differences between 25(OH)D concentrations after the intervention according to the addition of FOS.

We analysed changes in vitamin D concentrations according to body mass index (BMI) or the presence of obesity. We did not find a different response in the rise in vitamin D concentrations or in the percentage of women reaching adequate vitamin

D concentrations according to these characteristics (data not shown).

In the low dose group there was a significant increase in serum i-PTH at 12 and 24 months. In women supplemented with vitamin D₃, there was no statistically significant differences in i-PTH at 12 months, but there was a significant increase at 24 months. However i-PTH levels at 24 months were significantly lower in vitamin D group than in the low dose group (p=0.023).

Changes in BMD and bone turnover markers

We did not find significant changes in BMD in the low dose group throughout the study. After 24 months of intervention with higher dose vitamin D₃ there was a significant increase in BMD at femoral neck ($0.807 \pm 0.109 \text{ g/cm}^2$ vs $0.820 \pm 0.110 \text{ g/cm}^2$, p = 0.045). However, we did not find statistically significant differences in BMD at lumbar spine. Besides, we did not observe significant changes in the analysed bone turnover markers (CTX, OC and P1NP) in any of the intervention groups (Table 5).

Changes in anthropometric parameters, glucose, insulin and lipids

In the low dose arm we observed a small but significant increase in weight ($68.6 \pm 11.9 \text{ kg}$ vs $69 \pm 11.8 \text{ kg}$, p = 0.012) and total fat mass ($25.3 \pm 8.9 \text{ kg}$ vs $26.1 \pm 9.1 \text{ kg}$, p = 0.04) at 24 months. There were no significant changes in weight or body composition in women supplemented with vitamin D₃ (data not shown).

After the intervention with high-dose vitamin D₃-enriched milk, we observed a decrease in fasting plasma glucose at 12 months (90.9 ± 12.8 vs $88.1 \pm 16.3 \text{ mg /dl}$, p = 0.002) and at 24 months (90.9 ± 12.8 vs 88.8 ± 14.4 , p = 0.010). There was also a reduction in HbA_{1c} concentrations at 12 months ($5.9 \pm 0.4\%$ vs 5.7 ± 0.6 , p <0.001) and at 24 months ($5.9 \pm 0.4\%$ vs 5.7 ± 0.6 , p <0.001). However, we did not find significant changes in insulin concentrations or insulin resistance indexes. After adjustment for weight, results were unchanged.

There were no changes in lipid parameters in the low dose group. In women supplemented with higher doses of vitamin D₃, we observed a significant decrease in total cholesterol (-3.5 mg/dl at 12 months, p = 0.012, -5 mg/dl at 24 months, p < 0.001) and LDL cholesterol (-3.5 mg/dl at 12 months, p = 0.012, -5 mg/dl at 24 months, p < 0.001), and also in apo B (-16.5 mg/dl at 12 months, p <0.001, -13.3 mg/dl at 24

months, $p = 0.015$).

Discussion:

The present study shows that in postmenopausal healthy women the daily intake of milk enriched with calcium (900 mg/day) and vitamin D₃ (600 IU/day) induces a significant improvement in vitamin D status and a small increase in femoral neck BMD after 24 months. Moreover, a modest improvement in lipid profile and glucose homeostasis was observed.

Our data show that a simple nutritional intervention with vitamin D₃ and calcium enriched milk that supplies 600 IU/day and 900 mg/day respectively, is effective in increasing 25(OH)D concentrations and helps to reach adequate 25(OH)D levels in a high percentage of women. These results are comparable to those described with pharmacological supplements, which often are not well tolerated by patients, especially if combined with calcium. In addition, we found a small increase in BMD at femoral neck after 24 months of intervention.

We did not find any changes in bone turnover markers. **The effects on calcium and vitamin D supplementation on bone turnover markers are somewhat conflicting. In postmenopausal healthy women (mean age 57-60 years, baseline calcium intake 900 mg/day), Aloia et al¹⁸ showed that 1200 mg calcium/day reduced bone turnover markers, whereas supplementation with up to 100 ug of vitamin D₃/day does not. The authors concluded that 1200 mg/day of calcium supplements is more effective in reducing bone turnover than an unsupplemented intake of 900 mg/d. Thus, this fact may contribute to explain our findings, and maybe a higher supplementation with calcium is necessary to induce changes in bone turnover. Besides, we measured bone markers at baseline, 12 months and 24 months, so an effect of our intervention between baseline and 12 months may not be ruled out. Regarding this, in the study from Aloia et al¹⁷, the changes in bone turnover was observed at 6 months.**

The observed increase in i-PTH was lower in the higher dose vitamin D arms than in the low dose group. High PTH levels increase bone turnover and decrease BMD. In postmenopausal women, PTH levels above the reference interval increase risk of fracture in the presence of low vitamin D levels¹⁹. Thus, this nutritional intervention may attenuate the age-associated increase in i-PTH and may decrease

fracture risk.

Previous studies evaluating the effects of nutritional interventions including vitamin D supplementation in postmenopausal women have shown conflicting results. Manios et al.¹⁴ showed that the intervention with dairy products containing 300 IU/day of vitamin D₃ induced a decrease in bone turnover markers (CTX and OC) compared to calcium alone after 12 months. Similarly to our findings, they did not observe a reduction in i-PTH during the intervention although the increase in i-PTH concentrations in the control group was higher compared to the intervention groups (calcium and vitamin D group). Besides, there were no changes in lumbar spine BMD despite of positive changes in femoral neck BMD. In another study conducted in postmenopausal women aged 50–80 years old with a T-score in total hip or lumbar spine ≤ -2.0 ²⁰, there was no obvious benefit in 1 year treatment with a higher dose (6 500 IU/day) of vitamin D₃ supplementation compared to a standard dose of 800 IU/day. In certain subgroups, the standard dose of vitamin D was better than the higher dose regarding changes in hip BMD. In addition, standard-dose treatment led to greater reduction in serum P1NP as a measure of bone turnover. In another study from Bonjour et al.¹⁵, the consumption of cheese containing 100 IU of vitamin D₃ induced a decrease in TRAP5b but not in CTX after 12 weeks. Taken together these data, it seems that the relationship between vitamin D intake and bone turnover is not linear and may differ according to age, baseline bone turnover, and the time after the intervention analysed. Thus, in studies evaluating short-term changes^{15,16} in bone turnover after interventions with vitamin D₃ a decrease in some but not all bone turnover markers is shown, but the effects observed during long interventions¹⁴ are less clear. **Increasing milk intake reduces bone turnover by a similar amount to the reduction observed with calcium supplements, 20%**²¹. Again, the high baseline calcium intake in our study may have influenced our results on bone turnover markers.

This nutritional intervention also included a calcium supplementation, 600 mg/day in the control group and 900 mg/day in the intervention group. Calcium supplementation of about 1000 mg daily has demonstrated a significant preventive effect on bone loss in postmenopausal women for at least 4 years²², so the observed effect in BMD may be explained not only by the supplementation with vitamin D but also by the higher intake of calcium. Increasing calcium intake from dietary sources **has been shown to slightly increase BMD** by 0.6-1.8% over one to two years at all sites, except the forearm. The observed increases are small (1-2%) and non-progressive, with little further effect on BMD after a year¹¹. In our study, the 600 mg of

calcium included in the low dose milk may have influenced the small difference observed in BMD between the low dose group and the intervention group. Also, the higher baseline calcium intake may have influence the observed increase in BMD, at least in part.

In a previous study the effects of FOS on calcium absorption has been tested, with not significantly increase in calcium absorption¹⁷. The data of the present study are in accordance with these previous results, as no differences in vitamin D concentrations or serum calcium were observed according to the addition of FOS.

The effects of the supplementation with vitamin D on lipid profile are not well established. PTH has been reported to reduce lipolysis at least *in vitro*²³, so the reduction in PTH after vitamin D may decrease lipolysis. In addition, as suggested by Zittermann et al.²⁴, vitamin D could affect the serum lipids through an increased calcium level, which may reduce hepatic TG formation and/or secretion²⁵. Furthermore, vitamin D may indirectly influence lipid metabolism by its influence on glucose metabolism²⁶. Calcium supplementation has been shown to significantly reduce LDL cholesterol and to increase HDL cholesterol²⁷. Thus, although it is difficult to separate the effects on lipids of calcium and vitamin D in our study, the calcium supplementation may have influenced the improvement in lipids. In the present study, the supplementation with vitamin D induced a modest decrease in total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol, while no effects on HDL cholesterol or triglycerides was observed. This data are in accordance with results from a meta-analysis, which suggest that vitamin D supplementation is beneficial for lipids, especially LDL cholesterol, but has little effect on HDL cholesterol, and triglycerides²⁸. Moreover, our data care in accordance with the effect observed in postmenopausal women from the WHI trial treated with calcium and vitamin D supplements²⁹, although with the advantages of a simple nutritional intervention. Besides, recent data demonstrate that apo B is a better measure of circulating LDL particle number concentration and is a more reliable indicator of risk than LDL-C³⁰. The decrease observed in apo B after the nutritional intervention confirms previous data and reinforces the beneficial effects on lipid profile and potentially on cardiovascular risk.

Regarding glucose-related parameters, we observed a decrease in fasting plasma glucose and glycated haemoglobin after the intervention with higher dose of vitamin D₃, which are in accordance with previous data from Pittas et al. in healthy older adults treated with calcium and vitamin D³¹. However, we did not find any significant changes in insulin or insulin resistance index (homeostasis model

assessment, HOMA), as has been reported by Wood et al. in postmenopausal women treated with vitamin D supplements³². In a recent paper from Sorkin et al.³³ an inverse relationship between 25 OH vitamin D and fasting plasma glucose was demonstrated, and evidence for a threshold effect on HOMA was found. This finding may explain the lack of effect on insulin-resistance in our study despite of a decrease in fasting plasma glucose in women taking higher dose vitamin D₃ enriched milk.

Our study has several strengths, as the randomized and double blind design, a long follow up, and the exhaustive evaluation of bone metabolism, lipid profile and glucose metabolism. Limitations of the study are the absence of evaluation of fractures, and the absence of a comprehensive assessment of physical activity which may have influence the results. However, women were advised not to change their lifestyle habits and exercise was evaluated semi-quantitatively and showed no changes during the intervention. **Moreover, we measured bone turnover markers at baseline, 12 months and 24 months, which may have been too late to observe the response.** Besides, we cannot totally exclude a possible effect of FOS on the absorption of nutrients, different from vitamin D and calcium, which may influence the results. However, the absence of differences in vitamin D concentrations, or in serum calcium, according to the presence of FOS indicate that, if these differences exists, they may be of limited extent. Finally, we are aware that the effects observed after this nutritional intervention are of limited magnitude, and that a higher intake of vitamin D may have increased the results. However, our results must be considered in the context of a nutritional intervention in healthy postmenopausal women, relatively young, without osteoporosis or other bone diseases.

In summary, in healthy postmenopausal women a straightforward nutritional intervention with an enriched milk supplying a daily intake of 600 IU of vitamin D₃ and 900 mg of calcium improves vitamin D concentrations and induces potentially favourable changes in bone mass, lipid profile and glucose homeostasis. Thus, this nutritional intervention may be of special utility in postmenopausal women, which have increased risk of osteoporosis and cardiovascular events. Further studies are needed to elucidate whether the small changes in BMD, glucose, and lipid profile could be clinically relevant after extending this nutritional intervention at long-term.

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Tables and figure legends:

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of study subjects.

	Group L (n = 152)	Group A (n = 157)	Group B (n = 152)
Age (years)	59.5 ± 5.3	59.8 ± 5.2	59.9 ± 6.3
Years since menopause	9.7 ± 5.2	10.1 ± 5.1	9.8 ± 5.4
Weight (kg)	68.8 ± 11.5	71.1 ± 12.3	70.0 ± 11.2
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.6 ± 4.5	28.4 ± 4.9	27.9 ± 4.6
25 OH vitamin D (ng/ml)	21.8 ± 7.1	21.4 ± 6.7	22.3 ± 9.4
i-PTH (pg/ml)	57.6 ± 22.2	59.7 ± 21.2	58.4 ± 23.2
Serum calcium (mg/dl)	9.9 ± 0.6	9.7 ± 0.6	9.7 ± 0.7
LS BMD (g/cm ²)	0.955 ± 0.140	0.985 ± 0.139	0.957 ± 0.128
FN BMD (g/cm ²)	0.798 ± 0.106	0.817 ± 0.108	0.803 ± 0.108
CTX (ng/ml)	0.673 ± 0.383	0.671 ± 0.397	0.678 ± 0.363
OC (ng/ml)	16.6 ± 8.0	15.5 ± 6.8	17.1 ± 7.1
P1NP (ng/ml)	10.9 ± 3.4	10.5 ± 3.0	11.4 ± 3.4
FPG (mg/dl)	88.5 ± 14.4	89.4 ± 13.8	89.4 ± 12.8
Insulin (mcU/ml)	7.5 ± 4.4	7.7 ± 4.0	7.8 ± 7.5
CT (mg/dl)	209.5 ± 32.7	213.5 ± 32.7	209.3 ± 33.2
HDL (mg/dl)	53.0 ± 13.5	54.0 ± 13.6	56.8 ± 16.0*
LDL (mg/dl)	137.9 ± 31.2	144.6 ± 32.3	134.6 ± 30.2
TG (mg/dl)	92.5 ± 44.7	94.2 ± 41.7	89.4 ± 49.4
Apo B100 (ug/ml)	221.2 ± 90.3	233.7 ± 91.1	228.8 ± 97.3
HbA _{1c} (%)	5.9 ± 0.42	5.9 ± 0.45	5.8 ± 0.38

Intervention arms: L: low dose group; A: vitamin D₃ enriched group; B: vitamin D₃ +FOS enriched group.

* p<0.05 for the comparison between groups L and B.

BMI: body mass index; i-PTH: intact parathyroid hormone; LS: lumbar spine; BMD: bone mineral density; FN; femoral neck; CTX: carboxy-terminal collagen crosslinks; OC: osteocalcin; P1NP: procollagen amino- terminal propeptide type 1; FPG: fasting

plasma glucose. CT: total cholesterol; HDL: high-density-lipoprotein; LDL: low-density-lipoprotein; TG: triglycerides.

Table 2: Baseline macronutrient intake.

	All	Group L (n = 152)	Group A (n = 157)	Group B (n = 152)
<u>Energy intake (kcal)</u>	<u>1694 ± 487</u>	<u>1564 ± 481</u>	<u>1591 ± 492</u>	<u>1701 ± 420</u>
<u>Carbohydrates (gr)</u>	<u>162 ± 59</u>	<u>159 ± 57</u>	<u>165 ± 61</u>	<u>170 ± 60</u>
<u>Fiber (gr)</u>	<u>19 ± 9</u>	<u>21 ± 10</u>	<u>17 ± 8</u>	<u>19 ± 8</u>
<u>Fat (gr)</u>	<u>75 ± 30</u>	<u>81 ± 31</u>	<u>76 ± 31</u>	<u>74 ± 29</u>
<u>MUFA (gr)</u>	<u>36 ± 15</u>	<u>40 ± 18</u>	<u>39 ± 21</u>	<u>36 ± 15</u>
<u>PUFA (gr)</u>	<u>10 ± 7</u>	<u>10 ± 6</u>	<u>11 ± 6</u>	<u>10 ± 5</u>
<u>SA (gr)</u>	<u>22 ± 11</u>	<u>21 ± 11</u>	<u>22 ± 9</u>	<u>22 ± 11</u>
<u>Cholesterol (mg)</u>	<u>284 ± 191</u>	<u>280 ± 190</u>	<u>189 ± 201</u>	<u>285 ± 189</u>
<u>Proteins (gr)</u>	<u>82 ± 29</u>	<u>87 ± 32</u>	<u>85 ± 27</u>	<u>81 ± 28</u>
<u>Calcium (mg)</u>	<u>918 ± 305</u>	<u>899 ± 301</u>	<u>922 ± 310</u>	<u>929 ± 300</u>
<u>Iron (mg)</u>	<u>12 ± 7</u>	<u>14 ± 8</u>	<u>12 ± 9</u>	<u>13 ± 7</u>
<u>Potassium (mg)</u>	<u>2959 ± 878</u>	<u>2988 ± 900</u>	<u>2944 ± 889</u>	<u>3002 ± 870</u>
<u>Magnesium (mg)</u>	<u>324 ± 110</u>	<u>301 ± 109</u>	<u>330 ± 99</u>	<u>320 ± 106</u>
<u>Phosphate (mg)</u>	<u>8.5 ± 3.2</u>	<u>9.0 ± 3.0</u>	<u>8.9 ± 3.1</u>	<u>8.4 ± 3.5</u>
<u>Vitamin D (ugr)</u>	<u>3.0 ± 5.2</u>	<u>3.2 ± 4.9</u>	<u>3.1 ± 5.0</u>	<u>3.0 ± 5.5</u>

MUFA: monounsaturated fatty acids; PUFA: polyunsaturated fatty acids; SA: saturated acids.

Table 3: Changes in dietary intake of calcium and vitamin D during the intervention.

	Group	Baseline	12 months	24 months
<u>Dietary calcium (mg)</u>	L (n = 130)	<u>899 ± 301</u>	<u>902 ± 310</u>	<u>908 ± 299</u>
	A (n = 125)	<u>922 ± 310</u>	<u>912 ± 309</u>	<u>919 ± 314</u>
	B (n = 125)	<u>929 ± 300</u>	<u>940 ± 295</u>	<u>935 ± 301</u>
<u>Dietary vitamin D (ugr)</u>	L (n = 130)	<u>3.2 ± 4.9</u>	<u>3.0 ± 4.8</u>	<u>3.1 ± 3.9</u>
	A (n = 125)	<u>3.1 ± 5.0</u>	<u>2.9 ± 5.2</u>	<u>2.9 ± 5.1</u>
	B (n = 125)	<u>3.0 ± 5.5</u>	<u>2.9 ± 5.1</u>	<u>3.0 ± 5.0</u>

Table 4: Changes in 25 OH vitamin D concentrations, bone mineral density and bone turnover markers.

	Group	Baseline	12 months	24 months
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25 OH vitamin D (ng/ml)	L (n = 130)	22.0 ± 7.3	23.7 ± 7.3*	22.6 ± 7.0
	A (n = 125)	21.3 ± 6.8	27.0 ± 9.1**	26.6 ± 6.4**
	B (n = 125)	21.9 ± 9.5	27.2 ± 11.0**	25.2 ± 6.2**
<u>Calcium (mg/dl)</u>	<u>L (n = 130)</u>	<u>9.91 ± 0.6</u>	<u>9.86 ± 0.54</u>	<u>9.86 ± 0.52</u>
	<u>A (n = 125)</u>	<u>9.73 ± 0.59</u>	<u>9.70 ± 0.64</u>	<u>9.79 ± 0.64</u>
	<u>B (n = 125)</u>	<u>9.67 ± 0.66</u>	<u>9.72 ± 0.53</u>	<u>9.83 ± 0.57</u>
i-PTH (pg/ml)	L	57.2 ± 22.5	60.9 ± 25.2*	62.2 ± 25.5*
	A+B (n = 250)	59.1 ± 24.5	60.1 ± 25.7	61.3 ± 26.3*
OC (ng/dl)	L	14.97 ± 6.87	14.84 ± 6.88	15.06 ± 6.23
	A+B	15.83 ± 6.86	15.49 ± 6.60	15.64 ± 6.91
CTX (ng/ml)	L	0.664 ± 0.428	0.657 ± 0.364	0.639 ± 0.335
	A+B	0.675 ± 0.411	0.675 ± 0.371	0.677 ± 0.402
P1NP (ng/ml)	L	10.05 ± 3.06	10.24 ± 3.34	10.4 ± 3.5
	A+B	10.45 ± 3.24	10.50 ± 3.25	10.58 ± 3.28
LS BMD (gr/cm ²)	L	0.995 ± 0.140	0.999 ± 0.142	1.004 ± 0.152
	A+B	0.978 ± 0.134	0.981 ± 0.134	0.991 ± 0.138
FN BMD (gr/cm ²)	L	0.815 ± 0.107	0.827 ± 0.113	0.829 ± 0.125
	A+B	0.807 ± 0.109	0.813 ± 0.110	0.820 ± 0.110*

Intervention arms: L: low dose group; A: vitamin D₃ enriched group; B: vitamin D₃ +FOS enriched group.

* p <0.05 compared to baseline. ** p <0.001 compared to baseline.

No differences were observed between groups L or A+B

i-PTH: intact parathyroid hormone; OC: osteocalcin; CTX: carboxy-terminal collagen crosslinks; P1NP: procollagen amino- terminal propeptide type 1; LS; lumbar spine; FN: femoral neck; BMD: bone mineral density.

Table 5: Changes in biochemical parameters during the intervention.

	Group	Baseline	12 months	24 months
Weight (kg)	L (n = 130)	68.6 ± 11.9	69.0 ± 11.9	69.0 ± 11.8*
	A (n = 125)	71.0 ± 12.7	70.6 ± 11.9	71.3 ± 13.1
	B (n = 125)	70.4 ± 11.9	70.3 ± 11.8	70.8 ± 12.3
Glucose (mg/dl)	L	89.0 ± 14.2	87.7 ± 19.9	89.6 ± 19.2
	A+B (n = 250)	90.9 ± 12.8	88.1 ± 16.3*	88.8 ± 14.4*
HbA1c (%)	L	5.9 ± 0.4	5.7 ± 0.5	5.7 ± 0.5
	A+B	5.9 ± 0.4	5.7 ± 0.6*	5.7 ± 0.6*
Insulin (mcU/ml)	L	7.2 ± 4.3	7.7 ± 4.0	7.3 ± 4.6
	A+B	7.8 ± 4.5	8.1 ± 5.2	7.4 ± 4.6
TC (mg/dl)	L	208.2 ± 33.1	210.9 ± 32.4	207.2 ± 30.4
	A+B	214.6 ± 33.7	210.9 ± 33**	209.6 ± 32.5**
HDL (mg/dl)	L	53.0 ± 13.6	55.2 ± 14.0	52.1 ± 13.6
	A+B	55.4 ± 15.2	55.5 ± 14.5	55.4 ± 14.2
LDL (mg/dl)	L	137.4 ± 32.1	139.0 ± 32.1	135.7 ± 30.6
	A+B	141.4 ± 31.9	137.9 ± 30.3*	135.7 ± 31.6**
TGs (mg/dl)	L	88.7 ± 42.9	91.8 ± 37.7	96.3 ± 55.9
	A+B	89.8 ± 46.0	93.0 ± 50.6	91 ± 47.9
Apo B (ug/ml)	L	231.8 ± 93.6	232.1 ± 100.1	235.6 ± 100.0
	A+B	244.8 ± 97.4	228.3 ± 87.2**	231.5 ± 89.5**
CRP (mg/dl)	L	0.41 ± 1.02	0.33 ± 0.57	0.28 ± 0.31
	A+B	0.35 ± 0.52	0.32 ± 0.46	0.31 ± 0.41

Intervention arms: L: low dose group; A: vitamin D₃ enriched group; B: vitamin D₃ +FOS enriched group **(Changes in dietary calcium are not included in the intervention of the study).**

* p <0.05 compared to baseline. ** p <0.001 compared to baseline.

TC: total cholesterol; HDL: high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; LDL: low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; TGs: triglycerides; CRP: C reactive protein.

Figure 1: Flow chart of patients enrolled in the study.

Figure 2: Percentage of patients reaching 25(OH)D >20 ng/ml and 25(OH)D >30 ng/ml in each group of study.

* $p < 0.05$ for the comparison between vitamin D₃ intervention groups and control group.